

Dual Mechanisms of LYN Kinase Dysregulation Drive Aggressive Behaviour in Breast Cancer Cells

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Summary

The SRC-family kinase LYN is highly expressed in triple-negative/basal-like breast cancer (TN/BLBC) and in the cell-of-origin of these tumors, c-KIT-positive luminal progenitors. Here we demonstrate LYN is a downstream effector of c-KIT in normal mammary cells and protective of apoptosis upon genotoxic stress. LYN activity is modulated by PIN1, a prolyl isomerase, and in *BRCA1*-mutant TN/BLBC PIN1 upregulation activates LYN independently of c-KIT. Furthermore, the full-length LYN splice isoform (as opposed to the Δ aa25-45 variant) drives migration and invasion of aggressive TN/BLBC cells, while the ratio of splice variants is informative for breast cancer-specific survival across all breast cancers. Thus, dual mechanisms – uncoupling from upstream signals and splice isoform ratios – drive the activity of LYN in aggressive breast cancers.

Keywords: BRCA1, LYN kinase, triple-negative/basal-like breast cancer, PIN1, ESRP1, c-KIT

Introduction

Breast cancers molecularly classified as basal-like breast cancer (BLBC) typically display the triple (ER/PR/HER2)-negative (TN) phenotype (Badve et al., 2011). The molecular etiology of sporadic TN/BLBC is still poorly understood, although germline *BRCA1* mutations predispose to TN/BLBC, and *BRCA1* silencing or dysfunction in the BRCA1 pathway can be found in sporadic TN/BLBC (Badve et al., 2011). Limited therapeutic options are currently available for TNBC; chemotherapy is often initially beneficial, but TNBC has a high risk of relapse (Liedtke et al., 2008) emphasizing the need to further elucidate its biology and identify targets for novel treatment options.

The mammary epithelium consists of luminal cells, including ER negative (ER-) progenitor-like and ER positive (ER+) differentiated cells, and basal cells. TNBC likely originates from luminal ER- progenitors and the gene expression profile of both *BRCA1*-mutation-associated and sporadic TNBC reflects a 'luminal progenitor-like' profile (Lim et al., 2009; Molyneux et al., 2010; Proia et al., 2011). Elucidating the molecular regulation of this cell subset is important to understand not only normal mammary cell homeostasis but also the origins of TNBC.

Mammary ER- luminal progenitors are characterised by expression of the membrane tyrosine kinase receptor c-KIT (Regan et al., 2012; Smart et al., 2011), required for growth and survival of these cells and to prevent differentiation (Regan et al., 2012; Tornillo et al., 2013). This population also expresses the SRC-family tyrosine kinase (SFK) LYN (Bach et al., 2017; Regan et al., 2012; Smart et al., 2011), a known effector of c-KIT signalling in haematopoietic cells (Shivakrupa and Linnekin, 2005). Other SFKs are expressed in the mammary epithelium but, other than LYN, only FYN has an expression pattern restricted to a specific population (basal epithelial cells) (Bach et al., 2017; Kendrick et al., 2008). Based on this co-expression, a c-KIT-LYN signaling axis in mammary epithelial progenitors is proposed.

Previous studies have largely focused on LYN function in hematopoietic cells and leukemia, and persistent activation/deregulation of LYN has been associated with imatinib resistance in BCR-ABL+ leukemia (Martins et al., 2015; Ptasznik et al., 2004; Wu et al., 2008a; Wu et al., 2008b). In breast cancer, LYN has been reported as over-expressed and a potential drug target in TNBC by a number of studies (Choi et al., 2010; Croucher et al., 2013; Hochgrafe et al., 2010; Molyneux et al., 2010; Regan et al., 2012; Smart et al., 2011). LYN point mutations in breast cancer are rare (0.6%; <http://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic>), but have been associated with anti-estrogen resistance in a subset of ER+ tumors (Schwarz et al., 2014); only 6 - 10% of breast cancers show *LYN* amplification (<http://www.cbioportal.org/index.do>; <http://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic>). Other mechanisms contributing to the underlying LYN dysregulation in TNBC remain to be defined, as does the potential wider role of LYN in breast cancer.

Here we demonstrate that LYN kinase is a transducer of c-KIT growth signals in the normal mammary epithelium. We show that LYN can also be activated by the Prolyl Isomerase PIN1, which is normally transcriptionally repressed by BRCA1. In *BRCA1*-deficient TNBC, loss of this transcriptional repression results in increased PIN1 levels, resulting in LYN being activated independently of c-KIT. Furthermore, we address the role of the two LYN splice isoforms in breast cancer, and find that only full-length LYN (*LYNA*), as opposed to *LYN*^{Δ25-45} (*LYNB*), promoted cell migration/invasion. *LYNA* is expressed more highly in TNBC than other breast cancer types; however, we find that a higher ratio of *LYNA* over *LYNB* is present in breast cancers of patients with shorter survival times, irrespective of tumor subtype. Therefore, our findings demonstrate dual mechanisms, uncoupling from upstream signals and changing splice isoform ratios, driving the activity of LYN in aggressive breast cancers. These mechanisms have the potential to be targeted therapeutically and the *LYNA::B* ratio is a biomarker which could identify patients who would benefit from such interventions.

Results

LYN kinase is regulated by c-KIT and promotes growth of normal mammary epithelial cells

We previously demonstrated that mammary ER- luminal progenitors express the membrane tyrosine kinase receptor c-KIT, which is required for the growth and survival of these cells and prevents their differentiation (Regan et al., 2012; Tornillo et al., 2013). To define the major components of the c-KIT signaling network in the mammary epithelium, we examined expression of c-KIT and its ligand Stem Cell Factor (SCF) in distinct normal mouse mammary cell populations (**Figure 1A**). The two splice variants of c-KIT, GNNK+ and GNNK-, were expressed primarily in luminal cells (particularly in the ER- luminal subpopulation) (**Figure 1B**). The two SCF isoforms, soluble (sSCF) and membrane bound SCF (mSCF), were both present at low levels in luminal cells, whereas basal cells showed the highest levels of total SCF, with almost exclusive expression of the sSCF form (**Figure 1B and 1C**).

LYN is a key effector of c-KIT signaling in haematopoietic cells and LYN and c-KIT expression in the mammary gland are correlated (Regan et al., 2012; Roskoski, 2005). LYN exists in two isoforms, LYNA (full length LYN) and LYNB (LYN^{A25-45}) (**Figure 1D**). When expression of these isoforms was analysed by semi-quantitative RT-PCR, both *LynA* and *LynB* were found in all mammary epithelial populations; however, there was an association between higher *LynA* and *c-Kit* expression in the luminal ER- compartment (**Figure 1B**). Therefore, the expression pattern of c-KIT, SCF and full length LYN in the mammary epithelium indicated the existence of a basal-to-luminal paracrine c-KIT signaling network, mediated by the soluble form of SCF (sSCF), along with an enrichment of a potential c-KIT effector, LYN, in the SCF-responsive luminal cells.

To determine the signaling cascade activated by c-KIT in mammary cells we treated primary mouse mammary epithelial cells with SCF and assessed the phosphorylation status of a series

of previously described c-KIT effectors (Roskoski, 2005). Addition of SCF caused a marked increase in c-KIT phosphorylation as well as up-regulation of phosphorylation levels of JAK2, STAT3, AKT and ERK1/2 with distinctive kinetics (**Figure 1E**). Phosphorylation levels of LYN at its positive regulatory site Y397 were elevated approximately 6-fold within 60 minutes of stimulation with SCF (**Figure 1F**) and SCF treatment induced an increase in LYN kinase activity as measured by an IP kinase assay (**Figure 1G**). Conversely, c-KIT inhibition, by using either shRNA against c-KIT or a specific anti-c-KIT blocking antibody (ACK2), led to a significant decrease in LYN phosphorylation (**Figure 1H and 1I; Figure S1A**).

As c-KIT is required for growth of normal mammary cells *in vitro* (Regan et al., 2012) and positively regulated LYN activity, we tested whether LYN depletion also affected mammary cell growth. Following *Lyn* knockdown with two distinct shRNAs (shLyn#1 or shLyn#2) (**Figure 2A**), primary mouse mammary epithelial cells exhibited defective growth (**Figure 2B**) and a significant reduction in the expression of the proliferation marker Ki67 (**Figure 2C; Figure S1B**). This effect was observed in both unsorted primary mammary epithelial cells and in the purified luminal ER- progenitor population (**Figure 2D,E; Figure S2A**). As we have previously observed (Jarde et al., 2016), *in vitro* growth potential in primary mammary epithelial preparations was largely restricted to the luminal ER- population (**Figure 2D; Figure S2A**). Furthermore, knockdown of *LYN* in the human 'normal' mammary epithelial cell line, MCF-10A, with two distinct shRNAs caused a significant reduction in relative cell growth and in Ki67 expression compared to shScr controls (Figure 2F,G), without obviously affecting acinar architecture (**Figure S2B**).

We next tested the ability of a constitutively active LYN (Y508F) mutant to rescue c-KIT knockdown. Whereas over-expression of wild-type LYNA (LYNA WT) had no effect on the viability of c-KIT knockdown cells, activated LYNA (LYNA CA) rescued the growth defect

(Figure S3A). In addition, when we examined the ability of LYN-depleted cells to activate c-KIT downstream effectors in response to SCF, we found that LYN knockdown specifically interfered with AKT phosphorylation upon c-KIT stimulation **(Figure S3B)**. Overall these findings support the model that c-KIT activates LYN kinase to transduce pro-growth/survival signals and activate the AKT pathway in mammary epithelial cells.

LYN is required for growth of BRCA1-deficient mammary tumor cells

We have previously demonstrated that *Brca1* mutation-associated breast cancers originate from luminal ER-negative progenitors (Molyneux et al., 2010) and that c-KIT and LYN are expressed in mouse *Brca1* mammary tumors (Regan et al., 2012). To determine whether, similar to non-transformed mammary epithelial cells, *Brca1* mutant cells are growth-dependent on the activation of the c-KIT signaling pathway, primary mouse *Brca1*-mutant mammary tumor cells transduced with lentiviruses expressing either one of two shRNAs against *c-Kit* (shKit#1 and shKit#2) or a control shRNA (shScr) were analyzed. In spite of reduced *c-Kit* expression, no change in cell growth was observed in shKit cells compared to shScr cells **(Figure S3C)**. Furthermore, unlike normal cells, *c-Kit*-depleted tumor cells had phospho-LYN levels similar to those of control cells **(Figure S3D)** and treatment of *Brca1*-tumor cells with the ACK2 c-KIT blocking antibody did not alter LYN phosphorylation status **(Figure S3E; contrast with Figure 1I)**. Likewise, c-KIT knockdown failed to affect phospho-LYN levels in three human c-KIT-positive breast cancer cell lines with low BRCA1 levels, HCC-38 (*BRCA1* silenced by methylation), HCC-1806 and MDA-MB-157 (*BRCA1* low due to downregulation by miRNA) (Garcia et al., 2011; Li et al., 2013) **(Figure S4A)**. However, c-KIT knockdown in a c-KIT-positive *BRCA1*-wild type cell line, HCC-1187, did suppress LYN phosphorylation **(Figure S4A)**. These results indicate that in *Brca1/BRCA1*-tumor cells, at least *in vitro*, c-KIT is dispensable for growth and does not regulate LYN activity.

To test whether LYN activity is required for growth of transformed cells, we evaluated the effects of LYN knockdown on *Brca1*-tumor cell growth. LYN knockdown markedly impaired growth of mouse *Brca1* tumor-derived cells in monolayer culture (**Figure 3A**) and, to a lesser extent, in three-dimensional (3D) culture conditions on Matrigel (**Figure 3B**). Staining of 3D-cultured tumor cells for the proliferation marker Ki67 showed that the number of proliferating cells was reduced by approximately 30% in shLyn-transduced cultures compared with control (**Figure 3C**). The protective effect of 3D culture was, at least in part, due to activation of integrin signalling pathways by extracellular matrix as both pre-coating 2D culture dishes with fibronectin or culture with an antibody which activates $\beta 1$ integrin signalling pathways significantly attenuated the effects of *Lyn* knockdown (**Figure S4B,C**). The kinase activity of LYN was required for its pro-survival functions as expression of an shRNA-resistant wild-type LYNA (LYNA* WT) was able to rescue the effect of shLyn-transduction, but expression of a kinase dead LYNA (T410K) mutant (LYNA* KD) was unable to do so (**Figure 3D**). The broad spectrum kinase inhibitor Dasatinib, which was able to block LYN Y397 phosphorylation in mammary epithelial cells in a dose-dependent manner (**Figure S4D**), inhibited growth of three mouse BRCA1 tumor-derived cell lines (IC₅₀ 0.1 – 1 μ M) and the human BRCA1-mutant HCC1937 line (IC₅₀ 0.1 μ M) (**Figure S4E,F**). There was no effect of LYN knockdown or Dasatinib treatment of mouse BRCA1 tumor cells on levels of SYK phosphorylation (**Figure S5A,B**), which is reported as downstream of LYN (Coopman et al., 2000; Keshvara et al., 1998; Li et al., 1999).

Use of two short hairpins targeting human *LYN* (**Figure 3E**) demonstrated that *LYN* knockdown in human breast cancer cells also significantly impaired cell growth in the *BRCA1*-mutated HCC1937 human breast cancer cell line (**Figure 3F**) and in cells from a *BRCA1*-mutant breast cancer patient derived xenograft (PDX) (**Figure 3G**). These effects, therefore, were consistent in both mouse and human cells.

Since LYN blockade effectively suppressed tumor cell growth *in vitro*, we next evaluated the effects of blocking LYN activity *in vivo*. Intra-peritoneal (IP) injection of Dasatinib strongly reduced LYN phosphorylation in the normal mammary epithelium of wild type mice (**Figure S5C**) and daily treatment with Dasatinib significantly inhibited growth of *Blg-Cre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* tumors (**Figure S5D,E**). Immunohistochemical staining for phospho-Histone H3 (p-H3) showed a lower number of mitotic cells in Dasatinib- compared to Vehicle-treated tumors (**Figure S5F**).

Reduction of cell numbers following constitutive *Lyn* knockdown made testing the effects of specific *Lyn* depletion by shRNA on tumor cell growth *in vivo* difficult. Therefore, a conditional *Lyn* knockdown system in which mouse *Brca1*-tumor cells expressed shRNA against *Lyn* under the control of doxycycline was established. Analysis of *Lyn* transcript levels after exposure to doxycycline confirmed that *Lyn* expression was reduced in inducible shLyn-carrying cells in the presence of doxycycline (**Figure 3H**). Notably, upon orthotopic cell injection in immunodeficient mice, administration of doxycycline resulted in a significant decrease in the growth of tumors derived from cells carrying inducible anti-*Lyn* shRNA (**Figure 3I**). Staining of tumor sections for the mitotic cell marker phospho-H3 revealed a reduction in the number of mitotic cells in samples from doxycycline-treated shLyn-tumors compared with controls (**Figure S5G**). Therefore, LYN kinase depletion suppresses *Brca1*-mammary tumor cell growth both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

***Brca1*-depletion leads to up-regulation of LYN kinase activity in a PIN1-dependent manner**

Our data show that in normal mammary epithelial cells LYN kinase activity is under the strict control of the c-KIT receptor, whereas in *Brca1*-mutant tumor cells LYN functions independently of c-KIT. We hypothesized that inactivation of *Brca1* itself might contribute to dysregulation of

LYN kinase activity. First, we analysed a panel of TNBC cell lines for LYN and phospho-LYN (Y397) levels. Three of the lines (MDA-MB-436, SUM-149, HCC1937) carry inactivating *BRCA1*-mutations; one (HCC38) has *BRCA1* promoter methylation; four (MDA-MB-157, HCC1806, MDA-MB-468, HCC70) have been reported as having low *BRCA1* expression (Buckley et al., 2016; Garcia et al., 2011; Gong et al., 2015; Li et al., 2013); six (MDA-MB-231, MDA-MB-453, BT-20, BT-549, HCC1143, HCC1187) are *BRCA1* wildtype. Total LYN levels were variable across the lines, however, when phospho-LYN levels were normalised to total LYN, TNBC cells with defective *BRCA1* had significantly higher levels of phospho-LYN than wild type cells (**Figure 4A**). Furthermore, *Brca1* knockdown in primary (normal) mouse mammary epithelial cells resulted in increased LYN phosphorylation but unchanged c-KIT phosphorylation (**Figure 4B**). Conversely, forced over-expression of *BRCA1* (HA-*BRCA1*) in primary mammary epithelial cells suppressed LYN phosphorylation (**Figure 4C**).

The prolyl isomerase PIN1 recognises specific serine-proline or threonine-proline sequences in proteins, changing the conformation of the prolines within these sequences and resulting in altered activity of the target protein (Zhou and Lu, 2016). LYN contains potential PIN1 consensus target sequences (Pro197 and Pro229) and PIN1 is transcriptionally repressed by *BRCA1* (MacLachlan et al., 2000). Therefore we hypothesised that increased LYN activity following *BRCA1* inactivation/depletion results from increased PIN1 levels, and that PIN1 was activating LYN. To test this, we first used phospho-protein arrays to demonstrated that both *BRCA1* over-expression and *PIN1* knockdown in MDA-MB-468 cells resulted in a significant reduction in phosphorylation of LYN but not its close family member SRC (**Figure S6A,B**). Moreover, we confirmed that *BRCA1* suppresses PIN1 expression by over-expressing *BRCA1* in MDA-MB-468 cells and showing that *PIN1* mRNA levels were reduced by approximately 50% (**Figure S6C**). We also compared PIN1 levels in mouse *Brca1* tumor cells and normal mouse

mammary epithelium and confirmed that PIN1 levels were significantly higher in the tumor cells **(Figure S6D)**.

Next, we stained a tissue microarray consisting of 15 germline *BRCA1*-mutant and 15 sporadic TNBC cases. Cases from *BRCA1* patients showed, overall, significantly more intense PIN1 staining than sporadic tumors **(Figure 4D,E)**. Given our findings that *BRCA1* loss results in PIN1 upregulation, we hypothesised that, even in sporadic breast cancers not linked to germline *BRCA1* mutation but which have low *BRCA1* levels through other mechanisms, levels of *BRCA1* and *PIN1* expression would be inversely correlated. We therefore investigated their expression patterns in sporadic TCGA breast cancer cases, and consistent with our hypothesis, observed an inverse correlation between *BRCA1* and *PIN1* expression levels **(Figure S6E)**.

To demonstrate a direct functional link between PIN1 expression and LYN activity, we knocked down PIN1 in primary mouse *Brca1* null cells **(Figure 5A)** and cells from a *BRCA1*-mutant human breast cancer cell line (HCC1937; **Figure 5B**) and the *BRCA1*-mutant PDX **(Figure 5C)**. In all cases, knockdown of PIN1 decreased active LYN phosphorylation and cell survival, mimicking the effect of LYN knockdown, but did not change c-KIT phosphorylation.

To further elucidate the relationship between LYN phosphorylation, PIN1 and *BRCA1*, we silenced *PIN1* in a broader panel of TNBC cell lines. In HCC-38, MDA-MB-436, HCC1395 and MDA-MB-468 cells (*BRCA1* defective), *PIN1* knockdown resulted in decreased LYN Y397 phosphorylation **(Figure S6F-J)**. In HCC1187 cells (*BRCA1* wildtype), *PIN1* knockdown did not affect phosphorylation **(Figure S6J)**; notably, in this line LYN was still regulated by c-KIT **(Figure S4A)**.

Importantly, co-IP demonstrated that in mouse *Brca1* null tumor cells PIN1 interacted with LYN (**Figure 5D**). Furthermore, generation of mutants in putative PIN1 consensus target sequences (**Figure 5E**), showed that Proline to Isoleucine mutation of either residue 197 or both 197 and 229 resulted in a significant increase in inhibitory LYN phosphorylation at the Y508 site (**Figure 5F**).

We next assessed whether the PIN1–LYN regulatory mechanism is likely to be more widely applicable than just to *BRCA1* breast cancer. We therefore knocked down PIN1 in *BRCA2* null mammary epithelial cells and in a panel of *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* null ovarian cancer cells. PIN1 knockdown significantly reduced LYN Y397 phosphorylation in a human *BRCA2*-mutant breast cancer cell line (**Figure S7A**) and in primary mouse *Brca2*-null tumor cells (**Figure S7B**). However, knockdown of *Brca2* in primary normal mouse mammary cells did not alter PIN1 or phospho-LYN levels (**Figure S7C**). PIN1 knockdown suppressed LYN Y397 phosphorylation in COV 362 cells (*BRCA1*-mutant ovarian carcinoma; **Figure S7D**), PEO-1 and PEO-4 cells (*BRCA2*-mutant ovarian carcinoma; **Figure S7E,F**) although not in KURAMOCHI cells (*BRCA2*-mutant ovarian carcinoma; **Figure S7G**). Therefore, regulation of LYN by PIN1 is a general (although not universal) mechanism but PIN1 is not regulated by BRCA2. These findings are consistent with transcriptional activity of BRCA1 being involved in PIN1 regulation, as previously shown (MacLachlan et al., 2000).

To further investigate the involvement of specific BRCA1 functional domains in the regulation of the PIN1–LYN axis, and the possibility that different clinically relevant BRCA1 mutants may have different effects on this axis, we re-expressed either the wild-type BRCA1 or clinically relevant BRCA1 missense mutants (C61G in the RING domain, L1407P in the CC motif and A1708E in the BRCT domain) (Anantha et al., 2017) in the HCC1937 human *BRCA1*-deficient breast cancer cell line. We found that re-expression of both the wildtype and C61G mutant

BRCA1 resulted in both decreased PIN1 levels and decreased LYN phosphorylation while expression of the L1407P and A1708E mutations showed no significant differences compared to control *BRCA1*-mutant cells (**Figure 5G**). Therefore, mutation of the N-terminal RING domain (which disrupts binding to BARD1) does not alter the ability of BRCA1 to suppress the PIN1–LYN activation pathway. In contrast, mutation of the coiled-coil domain, affecting PALB2 binding (suggested to be critical for the activation of the BRCA1 transcriptional program as well as for DNA repair) (Anantha et al., 2017; Gardini et al., 2014) and of the C-terminal BRCT domains, important for interactions with Abraxas, BRIP1 and CtIP (Anantha et al., 2017) and known to be important for BRCA1 transcriptional activity (Hayes et al., 2000; Iofrida et al., 2012), do result in elevated levels of PIN1 and LYN activation. These support a model in which the transcriptional activity of BRCA1 is critical in the control of PIN1–LYN pathway activation.

Having established the BRCA1–PIN1–LYN axis, and given the important role of BRCA1 in repair of double-stranded DNA breaks, we examined whether LYN activity could affect the normal mammary cell response to DNA damage. Primary normal mouse mammary epithelial cells expressing a constitutively active LYN (Y508F) mutant (LYNA CA) were treated with the DNA damaging agent Methyl Methane Sulfonate (MMS), which causes double stranded breaks. Expression of LYNA CA led to a marked transient increase in Akt phosphorylation, suggesting elevated levels of survival signaling, and a significant reduction in cleaved PARP levels (**Figure S8A**) and TUNEL staining (**Figure S8B**), both markers of apoptosis, after MMS treatment relative to control cells. Consistent with this, levels of cleaved caspase-3 were significantly reduced in normal mammary cells expressing LYNA CA, compared to control cells, following treatment with 10 μ M cisplatin (**Figure S8C**) or exposure to 10Gy of ionising radiation (**Figure S8D**).

LYNA drives breast tumor cell aggressiveness

We next asked whether the two LYN isoforms, LYNA and LYNB, play different roles in breast cancer biology, independent of the BRCA1–PIN1–LYN axis. First, we transiently expressed GFP-tagged variants of LYNA and LYNB in MDA-MB-231 cells. After 48 hrs cells were fixed, counterstained with DAPI and analysed by confocal microscopy. Both LYNA and LYNB were predominantly membrane localised, with additional foci of intracellular staining, under these conditions (**Figure S9**).

Next, we used a *LYNA*-specific shRNA to knocked-down *LYNA* expression in MDA-MB-231 cells. shLynA cells displayed an approximate 60% reduction in LYNA protein levels compared to control (shScr) cells (**Figure 6A**). *LYNA* knockdown resulted in an overall decrease in cell proliferation (**Figure 6A**) and a strong reduction in cell migration and invasion *in vitro* (**Figure 6B**). To exclude the possibility that the impaired growth, migration and invasion of shLynA knocked-down cells was due to a reduction in total LYN levels rather than to depletion of the LYNA form, and to determine the specific contribution of each LYN variant to the malignant behaviour of the cells, we used a knockdown/reconstitution approach. Total *LYN* was knocked-down in MDA-MB-231 cells and then either a *LYNA* or a *LYNB* variant (*LYNA** or *LYNB**) not targetable by the Lyn shRNA was re-expressed. We assessed cell growth and the ability of the cells to migrate and invade relative to control cells. Total *LYN* knockdown led to a decrease in cell growth, but this could be equally rescued by either *LYNA** or *LYNB** (**Figure 6C**), indicating that these two distinct LYN isoforms can compensate for each other in promoting tumor cell growth. *LYN* knockdown significantly reduced the ability of the cells to migrate and invade; this could be completely rescued by *LYNA**, however, *LYNB** was unable to do so (**Figure 6D**). Therefore, while both LYN isoforms promoted tumor cell growth, only full length LYNA drove aggressive behaviour in these cells.

To determine whether LYNA and LYNB may associate with different protein partners, and whether this might explain their different effects on invasion/migration, we carried out a mass spectrometry analysis of proteins that interact with the two isoforms. LYN was knocked down in MDA-MB-231 cells and then either LYNA* or LYNB* re-expressed. We also expressed a LYNA* variant LYNA*^{Y32F} (**Figure S10A**). Y32 is located within the 21 amino acid segment present in LYNA and has been reported as being regulated by EGF signalling (Huang et al., 2013); if phosphorylation of this tyrosine was required for the differential behaviour of LYNA compared to LYNB, then we would predict LYNA*^{Y32F} would behave like LYNB. Cultures were established in duplicate and one set was treated with EGF prior to lysis (Huang et al., 2013). LYN was immunoprecipitated from these eight conditions (LYN KD, LYNA*, LYNB*, LYNA*^{Y32F}; all ± EGF) and lysates analysed by a Tandem Mass Tagging approach, which enables robust comparisons of relative levels of enrichment of identified proteins. The full results and differentially enriched proteins are provided in **Table S1**. Addition of EGF made little difference to the results, and there was little difference between the proteins which co-IP'd with LYNA* and LYNA*^{Y32F}, arguing against the hypothesis that LYNA*^{Y32F} was LYNB-like (**Figure S10B**). Indeed, the outcome of the analysis of the LYNA*-EGF, LYNA*+EGF, LYNA*^{Y32F}-EGF and LYNA*^{Y32F}+EGF pulldowns, four independent cell preparations, was very similar. Furthermore, the list of co-IP'd proteins included eight previously characterised LYN interacting proteins (ANKRD54, LIMA1, HNRNPK, MYH9, STAT3, PRKDC, EGFR, HSP90AB1) (Hein et al., 2015; Hornbeck et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2005; Kumar et al., 1998; Mertins et al., 2016; Petschnigg et al., 2014; Taipale et al., 2012; Tauzin et al., 2008; Van Seuning et al., 1995).

By comparison of LYN knockdown samples with LYNA*- and LYNB*-expressing samples, a number of proteins were identified which were differentially enriched in LYNA* samples. Using a cut-off for analysis of proteins which were enriched >1.2 fold in *both* the LYNA* pull down compared to the LYN KD pull down *and* in the LYNA* pulldown compared to the LYNB*

pull-down, we identified a list of 20 candidate LYNA interacting proteins. We carried out a Gene Ontology analysis using DAVID (Huang et al., 2009) of the differentially interacting proteins to begin to understand their functional significance. The list of proteins and the results of this analysis are provided in **Tables S2 and S3**. Notably, six of the proteins (ACTC1, ACTG2, KRT5, LIMA1, MYH3, TUBA1A; highlighted in green in **Table S3**), are associated with the cytoskeleton and its regulation, while two (LPXN, TNS1; highlighted in orange) are associated with integrins/cell adhesion. These findings suggest that LYNA and LYNB may interact differently with cell adhesions and the cytoskeleton, potentially explaining the effects of LYNA on migration and invasion.

LYN splicing is regulated by ESRP1

To determine what might regulate the balance between LYNA and LYNB expression, we first examined Affymetrix Human Exon 1.0ST array gene expression profiles of a breast cancer cohort from Guy's Hospital, London, and the TNBC subset of these cancers. Cohorts were split into '*High-LYNA*' and '*Low-LYNA*' expressing tumors (i.e.: above and below median expression of an Affymetrix probe 3098998, targeting uniquely the N-terminal region of LYNA) and the expression levels of 270 splicing regulators (the 'spliceosome'; **Table S4**) (Papasaikas et al., 2015) were interrogated. We found that in both all breast cancers (**Figure S10C**) and the TNBC subset (**Figure S10D**), *High-LYNA* tumors had significantly lower spliceosome levels than *Low-LYNA* tumors, indicating that splicing in general might be compromised in the *High-LYNA* group. Next, we examined the expression and effects on *LYN* splicing of a splicing regulatory protein (ESRP1/RBM35A) with putative consensus sequences in *LYN* intron 2 (**Figure S10E**) and which we hypothesised may be involved in the regulation of the balance of *LYN* splicing variants. We found that *ESRP1* levels were lower in *High-LYNA* breast cancers as a whole (**Figure S10F**) in the *High-LYNA* TNBC subset (**Figure S10G**). When *ESRP1* was knocked down in MCF7 cells (**Figure S10H**), which normally have a *LYNA::B* ratio of <2, the A::B ratio

was significantly increased to a mean of 2.5:1 (**Figure 6E**). Furthermore, when ESRP1 was over-expressed in MDA-MB-231 cells, which normally have a *LYNA::B* ratio of >3, this ratio was significantly reduced (**Figure 6F**). Therefore, a decrease in expression of the spliceosome in TNBC, and in particular ESRP1, could result in an increased *LYNA::B* ratio.

Patients with a high tumor *LYNA::B* ratio have shorter survival

As *LYNA* drives aggressive migratory and invasive properties in breast cancer, we asked whether total *LYNA* expression levels, or the relative amounts of *LYNA* and *LYNB*, might correlate with breast cancer with good or poor prognosis, or whether the *LYNA::B* ratio might have prognostic potential.

First, we analysed the relative expression of the *LYNA* and *LYNB* isoforms in samples of human normal mammary tissue as well as triple-negative (TN) and ER+/PR+ primary breast cancer. The ratio of *LYNA* to *LYNB* transcripts was close to 1 in the normal samples, but *LYNA* was preferentially expressed in TNBC (**Figure S11A**). No significant difference in relative *LYNA::LYNB* expression was observed in ER+/PR+ tumors compared to normal samples (**Figure S11A**). Similar results were observed in a small panel of human breast cancer cell lines (basal ER negative MDA-MB-231, MDA-MB-468, HCC-1143; luminal ER positive MCF7) (**Figure S11B**). However, while we could be confident that the tumor samples and cell lines in this analysis were predominantly composed of tumor cells, the 'normal tissue' samples had not been purified and likely contained a mixture of normal epithelial cell populations and non-epithelial cells. Therefore, for a more accurate assessment of *LYNA::B* ratio in normal human tissue, we used established flow cytometry protocols to purify the basal, luminal progenitor, luminal ER+ differentiated and stromal cell populations from reduction mammoplasty samples from four individuals (**Figure 7A-C** and **Figure S12**). Analysis of *LYNA::B* demonstrated that the luminal progenitor population had a significantly higher ratio than the other populations and,

indeed, that the *LYNA::B* ratio in normal cells was, in fact, in a similar range to the tumor samples.

To expand our analysis, we investigated a panel of breast cancer cell lines (Heiser et al., 2012) and the Guy's Hospital TNBC-enriched breast cancer cohort (Gazinska et al., 2013) for the expression of the *LYNA* isoform, using the Affymetrix probe 3098998. The *LYNA* sequence was significantly more highly-expressed in basal and claudin-low cell lines than in luminal cell lines (**Figure S11C**) and in the Guy's dataset was more highly expressed in tumors classified by PAM50 (Parker et al., 2009) as basal (**Figure S11D**) or by immunohistochemistry as TNBC (**Figure S11E**).

Next we interrogated *LYNA* and *LYNB* expression in TCGA breast cancer RNAseq data. Consistent with the microarray-based results, *LYNA* was expressed more highly in TNBC than in Non-TNBC ($P=6.528e-18$, Wilcoxon Rank Sum test). Moreover, *LYNB* was also higher in TNBC than non-TNBC ($P=1.554e-20$, Wilcoxon Rank Sum test), although showed overall lower expression levels than *LYNA* ($P=2.23e-03$, Wilcoxon Rank Sum test for TNBC; $P=3.354e-22$, Wilcoxon Rank Sum test for non-TNBC) (**Figure 7D**). There was no difference in *LYNA::B* ratio between normal breast tissue, TNBC and non-TNBC in the TCGA dataset (**Figure 7E**).

When we investigated the distributions of *LYNA::B* ratios across all tumors, we noted that while most sample ratios were in the range seen in the purified normal breast cells (**Figure 7C**), there was a distinct population of breast cancers with a log₂ RSEM expression ratio >7 (**Figure 7F**). When this population was compared for time to breast cancer-specific death with the remaining TCGA breast cancer cases, it had a shorter median time for survival ($P=0.032$ for >7.3) (**Figure 7G**).

Discussion

We have identified an important role for the SRC family kinase LYN in molecular regulation of the normal mammary epithelium and two novel mechanisms regulating LYN activity in breast cancer. The prolyl isomerase PIN1 is transcriptionally repressed by BRCA1 and in TNBC with BRCA1 loss-of-function increased PIN1 expression results in activation of LYN independent of upstream c-KIT signalling. Furthermore, full-length LYN (LYNA), confers migratory and invasive properties on breast cancer cells and, importantly, a high *LYNA::B* isoform ratio predicts shorter breast cancer-specific survival irrespective of subtype.

Although it has been previously reported that LYN is one of the most highly expressed SRC-family kinases in the normal mammary gland (Bach et al., 2017; Kendrick et al., 2008; Smart et al., 2011), its function in this tissue has not previously been investigated. LYN associates with c-KIT in hematopoietic cells and participates in numerous SCF-induced responses by promoting either positive or negative downstream signaling depending on cell type and context (Shivakrupa and Linnekin, 2005). Our results now demonstrate that LYN is activated by c-KIT and is critical for SCF:c-KIT-dependent phosphorylation of AKT in mammary progenitors. However, given that LYN has been implicated in other signaling pathways promoting cell survival and proliferation (Shivakrupa and Linnekin, 2005), it cannot be ruled out that additional pathways in mammary progenitors may be regulated by LYN.

Activation of AKT in the mammary epithelium by LYN contrasts with B-lymphocytes, in which LYN negatively regulates AKT and opposes the tyrosine kinase SYK, an AKT activator in that system (Li et al., 1999). SYK is expressed in normal breast but lost in a subset of aggressive breast cancer cell lines and its re-expression has been reported to suppress malignant growth (Coopman et al., 2000); SYK has been reported as a target of LYN kinase activity in B cells (Keshvara et al., 1998). However, we have found no evidence of regulation of SYK catalytic

domain tyrosine phosphorylation by LYN. While this does not rule out other potential interactions between these kinases, it suggests that mutual regulation seen in B cells does not hold true in the breast.

c-KIT+/ER- mammary luminal progenitors are considered to be the cell-of-origin of BRCA1-mutated and sporadic TNBC (Lim et al., 2009; Molyneux et al., 2010) and, indeed, can give rise to a range of tumor types depending on the combination of genetic lesions used to initiate tumor formation (Melchor et al., 2014; Molyneux et al., 2010). Although *c-Kit* is highly expressed in *Brca1*-mutant mammary tumors (Regan et al., 2012; Smart et al., 2011), as well as in a subset of breast cancers within the TNBC groups (Jansson et al., 2014), targeting this receptor has not been an effective therapeutic approach (Chew et al., 2008; Yardley et al., 2009). Our findings may at least partly explain why these trials have failed. Although carriers of *BRCA1* germline mutations have an 80% lifetime risk of breast cancer, such cases make a small contribution to breast cancer in the general population. However, *BRCA1* was found to be silenced through promoter methylation in 14% of sporadic basal-like and 11% of non-basal-like breast cancers, while in two special subtypes of TN/BLBC, medullary and metaplastic breast cancer, promoter methylation was found in >60% of cases (Badve et al., 2011; Turner et al., 2007). Furthermore, *BRCA1* mRNA expression was two-fold lower in BLBC compared to matched controls and this was suggested to be dependent on upregulation of ID4, a negative regulator of BRCA1 transcription (Turner et al., 2007). BRCA1 levels can also be suppressed by other epigenetic mechanisms, such as activity of miRNAs (Garcia et al., 2011; Li et al., 2013). Therefore, activation of the PIN1–LYN axis by BRCA1 downregulation is more widely applicable than simply to BRCA1 germline mutation carriers.

Transcription of PIN1 is strongly suppressed by BRCA1 in a p53-independent manner (MacLachlan et al., 2000) but PIN1 can be aberrantly activated in human cancers by various

mechanisms in addition to BRCA1 loss-of-function. Changes in transcription, translation, and/or post-translational modifications can lead to abnormal activity of PIN1 in cancer (Zhou and Lu, 2016). In breast cancer, PIN1 transcription is upregulated following transformation by HER2 or RAS (Huang da et al., 2009), MAP3K8 activation (Iriando et al., 2015) or Dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP4) overexpression (Li et al., 1999). In addition to being a target for BRCA1 transcriptional activity, PIN1 is a direct transcriptional target of E2F (Huang da et al., 2009) and PIN1 transcription can be induced by Notch1 activation in mammary cells (Coopman et al., 2000). PIN1 mRNA stability is inhibited by microRNAs (miRNAs), including miR-200c (Keshvara et al., 1998) and miR-200b (Turner et al., 2007). Phosphorylation and/or sumoylation status of specific PIN1 residues have been reported to be critical for PIN1 substrate-binding and/or catalytic activity. Specific enzymes responsible for these modifications have been also identified (Zhou and Lu, 2016).

PIN1 specifically catalyzes *cis/trans* proline isomerization within phosphorylated Ser/Thr-Pro motifs with important effects on phosphorylation-dependent signalling. Numerous oncogenes and tumor suppressors are directly regulated by PIN1 (Zhou and Lu, 2016), and here we show that PIN1 is an important contributor to LYN hyper-activation in BRCA1-mutant tumor cells. Consistent with the fact that PIN1 substrates typically contain one or few target motifs, LYN has only two putative PIN1 consensus sites (Ser¹⁹⁶-Pro¹⁹⁷ and Ser²²⁸-Pro²²⁹). Whereas LYN phosphorylation at Ser¹⁹⁶ is only predicted, phosphorylation at Ser²²⁸ has been previously observed during cell cycle progression (Daub et al., 2008), although the specific kinase/s involved is/are still unknown. Interestingly, these two sites are located in the SH2 domain and in the SH2-Kinase domain linker segment, respectively, which are involved in intra- and/or inter-molecular interactions critical for the regulation of the open/closed LYN conformation, suggesting that local structural changes upon proline isomerization are likely to affect LYN activation status. Our findings suggest that regulation of LYN by PIN1 is a widely applicable

mechanism of regulation of this SFK. Our findings suggest SRC is not a target of PIN1 (Figure S5B); whether other SRC-family kinases are PIN1 targets remains to be investigated.

The link between BRCA1 loss-of-function and LYN activation, and the activation by LYN of signaling pathways which promote cell survival, growth and invasion is an important finding. In normal cells, the absence of functional BRCA1 results in genomic instability, which leads to p53 activation, followed by cell cycle arrest and apoptosis (Roy et al., 2012), implying that additional molecular alterations are required for *BRCA1*-mutant cells to survive and undergo malignant transformation. Not surprisingly, *TP53* mutations are frequently present in *BRCA1*-associated mammary tumors (Roy et al., 2012). As LYN hyperactivation suppresses cell death induced by DNA damage (Gamas et al., 2009; Zonta et al., 2014), aberrant LYN activation following *BRCA1* loss could facilitate progression towards tumorigenesis, allowing BRCA1 loss-of-function cells to survive long enough to accumulate *TP53* genetic alterations. Furthermore, activation of AKT downstream of LYN has been linked to ubiquitination and degradation of the p53 protein (Dos Santos et al., 2013; Iqbal et al., 2010) and this would enable functional suppression of the p53 pathway in BRCA1 mutant cells prior to genetic pathway suppression. Indeed, there is some evidence that LYN is generally anti-apoptotic (Aira et al., 2018), not only in the context of genotoxic therapies, and this warrants further investigation in breast cancer.

LYN amplification is rare in breast cancer, as are coding sequence mutations, (<http://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic>), although *LYN* activating mutations have been found in ER-positive breast cancers resistant to anti-hormone therapy (Schwarz et al., 2014). Genetic/genomic changes cannot therefore account for the elevated expression and deregulated function of this kinase which is characteristic of TNBC (Choi et al., 2010; Hochgrafe et al., 2010; Molyneux et al., 2010). Other mechanisms must make an important contribution to LYN deregulation in breast cancer. Deregulated kinase activity linked to BRCA1 loss-of-function

(whether due to germline changes or somatic silencing) is one such mechanism. However, we have also identified an additional mechanism, a change in the balance of LYN splice variants.

Alternative splicing is a critical post-transcriptional regulatory mechanism for many cancer-associated genes (Bonomi et al., 2013). LYN kinase exists as two isoforms, full-length LYN (LYNA) and LYN^{Δ25-45} (LYNB), differing by a 21-amino-acid insert found in the NH2-terminal unique domain (Alvarez-Errico et al., 2010). We have found that in breast epithelial cells, the balance between these transcripts is modulated by the splicing factor ESRP1. LYN has not been found among the ESRP1-regulated alternative spliced genes resulting from previous analyses (Shapiro et al., 2011; Warzecha et al., 2010; Warzecha et al., 2009), most likely due to the lack of representative probe sets in the array platforms used in those studies. Nevertheless, like LYN, known ESRP1 target genes play a role in cell motility, cell adhesion and/or epithelial-mesenchymal transition (Shapiro et al., 2011; Warzecha et al., 2010; Warzecha et al., 2009), indicating that co-regulation by ESRP1 of splicing transcripts for proteins that may function together with LYN in a pro-migratory and invasive pathway in TNBC cells.

We find that patients with breast cancer with a high *LYNA::LYNB* ratio have a shorter time to breast cancer death. Biologically, this clinical phenotype could be a result of *LYNA* conferring migratory and invasive properties on breast cancer cells. Exactly how alteration of the *LYNA::LYNB* ratio can generate signal outputs leading to cancer cell aggressiveness remains to be fully defined. Previous analysis of *LYNA* and *LYNB* function in mast cells revealed the two isoforms associate differentially with phosphoproteins (Alvarez-Errico et al., 2010), indicating that the 21-aa sequence governs protein interactions. Moreover, *LYNA* was more potent than *LYNB* in activating PLC γ and downstream Ca²⁺ signaling (Alvarez-Errico et al., 2010). In addition, unlike *LYNB*, *LYNA* kinase activity can be enhanced through phosphorylation by EGFR at a specific tyrosine residue (Y32) within the 21-aa-insert (Huang et al., 2013). However,

in an analysis of proteins differentially interacting with the LYN isoforms, we saw little effect either of EGF stimulation or of a Y32F mutation in the 21aa insert. We did find that LYNA interacted more strongly with proteins associated with the cytoskeleton, integrins and cell adhesion, pointing to differential effects of LYNA and LYNB on migration and invasion. This warrants further work.

Identification of patients who will respond to targeted, novel or repurposed therapies remains a major goal of clinical research. Our findings demonstrate that patients with BRCA1 dysfunction or with a high *LYNA::B* isoform ratio would be particularly likely to benefit from specific therapies targeting LYN kinase. Furthermore, our findings on the key dual mechanisms of LYN (dys)regulation, combined with emerging knowledge of its interaction partners (Zhu et al., 2013), will enable rational design of new compounds to specifically block the oncogenic signaling driven by LYN without the need to directly target the kinase domain, increasing treatment specificity and reducing the likelihood of off-target effects.

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STAR Methods

Detailed methods are included in the online version of the paper and include the following:

Key Resource Table

Contact for Reagent and Resource Sharing

Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the Lead Contact, Professor Matt Smalley (SmalleyMJ@cardiff.ac.uk).

Experimental Model and Subject Details

Animals

All animal work was carried out under UK Home Office project and personal licences following local ethical approval and in accordance with local and national guidelines, including ARRIVE guidelines. Normal primary mammary cells were prepared from fourth mammary fat pads of 10 week-old virgin female FVB mice. The *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* and *BlgCre Brca2^{fl/fl} p53^{fl/fl}* mice and the tumours they generate have been fully described previously (Hay et al., 2009; Melchor et al., 2014; Molyneux et al., 2010).

Human Tissue

Normal breast tissue was obtained from women (n = 4; aged 15, 24, 35, 39 years) undergoing reduction mammoplasty with no previous history of breast cancer. Patients provided written informed consent and the procedures were approved by the local Hospital Research Ethics Committee and by the 'Ethics Committee of Clinical Investigation of Euskadi'.

The human breast cancer patient-derived xenograft (PDX) BCM 3887 derived from a patient with a BRCA1 mutation (Zhang et al., 2013) was passaged in NOD *scid* gamma (NGS) mice.

The BRCA1 breast tumour (n=15) and normal triple negative breast cancer (n=15) tissue microarray was prepared by the Northern Ireland Biobank under ethical approval number NIB17-0232.

RNA samples from human tumour tissue were obtained from Breast Cancer Now Tissue Bank. Normal tissue samples were from reduction mammoplasties, selected to contain > 50% epithelium. All tumour samples (10 ER+PR+HER2- and 10 Triple Negative) were from primary tumours of no specific type, grade III, from pre-menopausal patients.

Cell lines

Cells were maintained at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere with the exception of MDA-MB-157, which were kept in L-15 medium with 10% FBS, streptomycin (100 ug/ml) and penicillin (100 U/ml) in a free gas exchange with atmospheric air.

MCF10A cells were maintained in DMEM/F12 supplemented with 5% horse serum, 20 ng/ml EGF, 10 µg/ml insulin, 1 ng/ml cholera toxin, 100 µg/ml hydrocortisone, 50 U/ml penicillin and 50 µg/ml streptomycin (growth medium). BT-549, KURAMOCHI, MCF-7, MDA-MB-231 and MDA-MB-436 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 medium with 10% FBS, L-glutamine (4 mM), streptomycin (100 ug/ml) and penicillin (100 U/ml). HCC-38, HCC-70, HCC-1143, HCC-1187, HCC-1395, HCC-1599, HCC-1806 and HCC1937 cells were cultured in modified RPMI-1640 medium (ATCC 30-2001) supplemented with 10% FBS, streptomycin (100 ug/ml) and penicillin (100 U/ml). COV-362, MDA-MB-453 and MDA-MB-468 cells were grown in DMEM with 10% FBS, streptomycin (100 ug/ml) and penicillin (100 U/ml). HCC1937 and MDA-MB-468 cells stably over-expressing BRCA1 were previously generated (Buckley et al., 2011) and were grown in the presence of puromycin (1 ug/ml). BT-20 cells were grown in MEM added with 10%

FBS, non-essential amino acids (0.1 mM), L-glutamine (2 mM), sodium pyruvate (1 mM), streptomycin (100 ug/ml) and penicillin (100 U/ml). PEO-1 and PEO-4 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 medium with 10% FBS, L-glutamine (2 mM), sodium pyruvate (2mM) streptomycin (100 ug/ml) and penicillin (100 U/ml). SUM-149 cells were grown in Ham's F-12 medium containing 5% FBS, HEPES (10 mM), insulin (5 ug/ml), hydrocortisone (1 ug/ml), streptomycin (100 ug/ml) and penicillin (100 U/ml). See Key Resources Table for more details.

Method Details

Isolation of and culture of normal mouse mammary epithelial cells

All animal work was carried out under UK Home Office project and personal licences following local ethical approval and in accordance with local and national guidelines, including ARRIVE guidelines.

Single cells were prepared from fourth mammary fat pads of humanely killed 10 week-old virgin female FVB mice . Intramammary lymph nodes were removed prior to tissue collection. Fat pads were finely minced on a McIlwain Tissue Chopper (source; add to table) and then digested for one hour at 37°C in 3 mg/ml collagenase A / 1.5 mg/ml trypsin (both from Sigma, Poole Dorset, UK) in serum-free L15 medium (ThermoFisher Scientific, Life Technologies, Paisley, UK) with gentle rotation. Tissue fragments ('organoids') released from the fat pad were washed and then incubated for 5 minutes in Red Blood Cell Lysis buffer (Sigma), washed and then plated for one hour at 37°C in DMEM/10%FBS (ThermoFisher) to partially purify fibroblasts by differential attachment. Organoids were then poured off, pelleted, washed twice with versene (ThermoFisher) and then incubated for 15 minutes in serum-free Joklik's Low Calcium medium (Sigma) at 37°C. They were then pelleted and resuspended in 2mls of 0.25% trypsin / 0.02% EDTA in HBSS (Sigma) and incubated for two minutes 37°C to release single epithelial cells. 5 mls of 5 µg/ml DNase I (Sigma) in serum-free L15 was then added to digest DNA liberated from

any lysed cells. Single epithelial cells were then pelleted and washed in L15/10% FBS (ThermoFisher Scientific, Life Technologies, Paisley, UK) and then resuspended at 10^6 cells/ml in L15/10% FBS (Regan et al., 2012; Smalley, 2010; Smalley et al., 2012).

Cell suspensions were stained with combinations of anti-CD24-FITC (1.0 μ g/ml; BD Biosciences, Oxford, UK), anti-CD45-PE-Cy7 (1.0 μ g/ml; BD Biosciences), anti-Sca-1-APC (1.0 μ g/ml; eBioscience, Hatfield, UK) or anti-Sca-1-PE (1.0 μ g/ml; BD Biosciences) antibodies and DAPI. Cells were then sorted on a FACSAria flow cytometer (BD Biosciences) excluding non-single cells by Time-Of-Flight analysis, dead cells by DAPI staining and leukocytes by CD45 staining. Basal mammary epithelial cells were defined as CD24^{+/Low} Sca-1^{Negative}. Luminal ER negative progenitor cells were defined as CD24^{+/High} Sca-1^{Negative}. Luminal ER positive differentiated cells were defined as CD24^{+/High} Sca-1^{Positive}. Cells incubated in non-specific IgG were used to set the limits of negative and positive staining for each antibody (Regan et al., 2012; Smalley, 2010; Smalley et al., 2012).

For 3D cultures, cells were resuspended in complete growth medium (DMEM:F12 with 10% FBS (ThermoFisher Scientific), 5 μ g/ml insulin (Sigma, Poole, UK), 10 ng/ml cholera toxin (Sigma) and 10 ng/ml epidermal growth factor) supplemented with 2.5% growth factor reduced Matrigel (BD Biosciences, Oxford, UK) and plated in 96- or 48- well plates onto Matrigel (40 μ l or 100 μ l per well, respectively). Cultures were maintained at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂/5%O₂ atmosphere in a Galaxy 170R incubator (New Brunswick, Eppendorf, Stevenage, UK). Stimulation with soluble murine SCF (Peprotech, London, UK) (100 ng/ml) and treatment with anti-c-Kit (ACK2) or IgG isotype control antibodies (50 μ g/ml) were carried out after starving cells for 12 hours.

Phase-contrast images were taken using a Leica MI6000B microscope (10X PH1 objective) and the LAS AF software.

Preparation and flow cytometric separation of normal breast cells from reduction mammoplasty

Normal breast tissue was obtained from pre-menopausal women undergoing reduction mammoplasty, with no previous history of breast cancer, who gave their informed consent. All samples were confirmed by histopathological examination to be free of malignancy. Immediately upon arrival at the laboratory, breast tissue was cut up manually into small pieces (approximately 0.5 cm cubed). Breast material was incubated in an equal volume of Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) (Gibco) supplemented with 5% foetal calf serum (FCS) and collagenase (Type I, Sigma) to a final concentration of 0.2 mg/ml, and digested (while shaking) overnight at 37° C. Following enzyme digestion, breast cells were washed and the organoids separated from any undigested material. The organoids were then isolated from blood cells, fibroblasts and endothelial cells by sequential filtration and back flushing from 140 and 53 µm pore size polyester monofilament meshes. Organoids were then disaggregated with 0.05% trypsin-EDTA and finally filtered through a 40 µm sieve (BD) to yield a predominantly single cell suspension. Cells were immediately processed for flow cytometric cell sorting on the basis of CD49f, ESA and 7-AAD staining (see **Figures 7** and **S12**) (Iriondo et al., 2015).

For CD49f/ESA staining, FITC-conjugated anti-ESA antibody and APC-conjugated anti-CD49f antibody were used (see Key Resources Table). In all cases, control samples were stained with isotype-matched control antibodies; the viability dye 7-aminoactinomycin D (7AAD) (BD) was used for dead cell exclusion and fluorescence minus one (FMO) controls were used to define the gates (Iriondo et al., 2015). In all cases, cells were analysed and sorted using a FACSAria (Becton Dickinson) flow cytometer. Data were analysed using FACSDiva software.

Primary tumour cell isolation and culture

Primary epithelial cells (from three distinct tumours (namely #1, #2, #3) from each mouse model or from three PDX implants) were obtained using the gentle MACS™ Dissociator and Mouse Tumour dissociation kit (Miltenyi Biotec, Bisley, Surrey, UK) following the manufacturer's recommendations using the protocol for 'Dissociation of Tough Tumours' for mouse tumours and the protocol for 'Dissociation of Soft and Medium Tumours' for the PDX. To ensure efficient dissociation volumes of Enzyme D, Enzyme R and Enzyme A were scaled up according to the size of the tumour piece (100 µL, 50 µL and 12.5 µL respectively per each 0.5 cm³). The optional steps - the short spin up for collection of the dissociated material at the bottom of the MACS tube and red blood cell lysis - were included in the procedure.

Mouse cells were cultured in complete growth medium in 2D adherent conditions for expansion or in 3D for functional studies. Cells up to passage 5 were used for all the experiments in this study. Freshly isolated human PDX cells were grown in HuMEC Ready Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific) in 3D onto Matrigel. Cultures were maintained at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂/5%O₂ atmosphere in a Galaxy 170R incubator (New Brunswick, Eppendorf).

Protein extraction and western blot analysis

3D cultured primary mammary cells were released from Matrigel using the BD cell recovery solution and lysed in Laemmli buffer. Protein extracts were separated by SDS-PAGE, transferred to PVDF membranes (IPVH00010, Merck Millipore, Hertfordshire, UK) and immunoblotted with antibodies detailed in the Key Resources Table. GAPDH or alpha-tubulin were used as loading controls. Resulting immunocomplexes were detected by HRP-conjugated anti-mouse IgG or anti-rabbit IgG secondary antibodies and enhanced chemiluminescent (ECL) reagents (WBLUF0100, Merck Millipore). Protein extracts (400 ug) from Ctr, BRCA1-, siCtr- and

siPin1-MDA-MB-468 cells were processed and analyzed for phosphorylation of LYN (Y397) and SRC (Y419) using the Human Phospho-Kinase Antibody Array (R&D Systems) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Immunoprecipitation (IP) LYN kinase assay

Once recovered from Matrigel, 3D cultured cells were lysed in RIPA buffer (50mM Tris/HCl, pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 1% Triton X-100, 1% Na deoxycolate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with 1mM Na orthovanadate and protease inhibitor-cocktail (Roche, Burgess Hill, West Sussex, UK). After centrifugation (14000 g for 10 min at 4°C), supernatants (150 µg of protein per sample) were pre-cleared with protein A-sepharose beads (GE Healthcare, Cardiff, UK) for 45 min at 4°C prior to incubation with anti-LYN antibodies (rabbit polyclonal sc-15) for 2 hours at 4°C. Immunocomplexes were pulled down after binding to protein A-sepharose beads (GE Healthcare) for 45 min at 4°C and washed twice with 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4, 5 mM MgCl₂, 3 mM MnCl₂ 1mM, 1mM Na orthovanadate (kinase buffer). Beads were then resuspended in 50 µL of kinase buffer with 2.75 µg of acid denatured enolase (Sigma), 5-10 µCi of $\gamma^{32}\text{P}$ ATP (PerkinElmer, Seer Green, Buckinghamshire, UK) and 1 µM cold ATP. After a 10 min-incubation at 30°C, the reaction was stopped by adding 13 µl of 10mM ATP, 50 mM EDTA and samples were subjected to SDS PAGE on a 10% acrylamide gel. Gels were fixed in 10% methanol/ 10% acetic acid solution, then dried and developed by autoradiography. Intensities of bands corresponding to phosphorylated enolase were measured using the Image J software.

LYN-PIN1 co-immunoprecipitation

Primary *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* mouse tumour cells were collected in cold PBS pH 8.3 buffer with 10 mM EDTA, 0.1 % Tween 20, 10 mM Sodium Fluoride, 1 mM Sodium Orthovanadate, 10 mM Sodium Pyrophosphate, 100 mM β -Glycerophosphate, 2 mM PMSF, complete Protease

Inhibitors (Roche) and lysed by passing through a 26G needle. After centrifugation (14000 g for 15 min at 4°C), supernatants (3-4 mg of protein) were pre-cleared with protein A-sepharose beads (GE Healthcare) for 45 min at 4°C prior to incubation with anti-Pin1 (rabbit polyclonal (H-123), sc-15340, Santa Cruz) or control (IgG) antibodies overnight at 4°C. After incubation with protein A-sepharose beads for 45 min at 4°C, immunoprecipitates were pulled down by centrifugation (900 g for 5 min at 4°C), washed five times with lysis buffer and eluted with Laemmli buffer. Samples were then resolved by SDS-PAGE on 10% polyacrylamide gels (15 x 15 cm). Western blot analysis was carried out as described above.

Gene expression analysis

With the exception of purified human primary cell populations (see below), RNA was extracted using the RNeasy Mini Kit (QIAGEN, Manchester, UK) from freshly isolated primary mouse mammary cells and 2D cultured cells. Alternatively, Trizol reagent (ThermoFisher Scientific, Paisley, UK) was used for RNA isolation from 3D cultured cells. cDNA synthesis was carried out using QuantiTect Reverse Transcription Kit (QIAGEN) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Semi-quantitative PCR reactions (28 cycles) were performed using GoTaq® PCR Core System reagents (Promega, Southampton, UK) and up to 120 ng of cDNA as template. Primers are listed in **Table S5**. PCR products were separated by electrophoresis on a 2% agarose gel with the exception of c-Kit PCR products, which were resolved on a 4% agarose gel.

Quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) was carried out using TAQMAN (Applied Biosystems, Life Technologies, Paisley, UK) Assays-on-Demand probes or Fast SYBR green Master Mix (**Table S5**) on freshly isolated RNA. Results were analysed using the $\Delta\text{-}\Delta\text{Ct}$ method normalised to β -actin or GAPDH and expressed as relative to a comparator sample.

For normal primary human breast cell populations purified by flow cytometry, RNA was isolated using the Machery-Nagel NucleoSpin RNA, according to instructions of the manufacturer. DNase-treated RNA was used to synthesize cDNA using SuperScript VILO cDNA Synthesis Kit (Invitrogen, 11754050), following the manufacturer's protocol. Semi-quantitative-PCR was performed using Phusion High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase (ThermoFisher Scientific, F530S) and Deoxynucleotide (dNTP) Mix, PCR Reagents (Sigma, D7295) on a MyCycler thermal cycler (Bio-Rad). 10 ng of cDNA was used as template and amplified using the following conditions: 95°C for 15 min, 22 cycles of amplification (95°C for 30 sec, 59°C for 30 sec, 72°C for 1 min) and a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. Primer (Invitrogen) sequences can be found in the **Table S5**. Finally, PCR products were separated by 1.5% agarose gel and stained with GelRed Nucleic Acid Gel Stain (Biotium). GAPDH was used as an internal control.

Cell viability and growth assays

Cell density in 2D cultures of primary cells and HCC1937 was determined by absorbance measurement following fixation and staining with crystal violet. CellTitreGlo cell viability reagent (Promega, Southampton, UK) was used to assess relative cell number of 3D cultured primary cells and MDA-MB-231 cells. The GelCount platform and software (Oxford Optronix, Oxford, UK) were used to automatically determine the size of organoids grown in 3D.

Cell migration and invasion assay

Invasion and migration assays were performed using 24-well Transwell inserts (Corning, Amsterdam, The Netherlands) coated or not with Matrigel, respectively. After 24 hour-starvation cells (75.000) were resuspended in serum-free (250 µL) medium and seeded into the upper chamber. 750 µL of medium supplemented with 10% serum was added to the lower chamber. After 20 hours, cells on the lower side of the insert were fixed, stained with crystal violet and counted under a light microscope.

siRNA Transfection

MDA-MB-468 cells were transfected with Pin1 or control siRNA (**Table S5**) using Lipofectamine RNAmix reagent (ThermoFisher Scientific) in Opti-MEM serum-free medium (ThermoFisher Scientific). MCF7 cells were transfected with control (Non-Targeting siRNA Pool #1, Dharmacon; see Key Resources Table) or ESRP1 siRNA (ON-TARGETplus, Dharmacon; see Key Resources Table) using DharmaFECT 4 Transfection Reagent (Dharmacon). All analyses were performed 72 hours after transfection.

Lentiviral vectors and cell transduction

pLKO.1 lentiviral vectors carrying shRNA directed to Brca1, c-Kit and Lyn were selected from the corresponding pLKO.1 target gene MISSION TRC shRNA sets (Sigma; see Key Resources Table). The c-Kit knockdown oligos target both c-Kit isoforms.

For *LYNA*, *PIN1*, *c-KIT* and *Brca2*, *Pin1* knock-down experiments, DNA Oligonucleotide pairs for shRNA specifically targeting *LYNA*, *PIN1*, *Pin1* or shScr were ligated into the pENTR™/U6 Gateway system entry vector (ThermoFisher Scientific). Hairpin sequences were verified and then transferred, together with the U6 promoter, into a Gateway- modified pSEW lentiviral vector (Regan et al., 2012) by LR reaction (ThermoFisher Scientific). ORFs for *Lyn* mutants (*LynA* CA and *Lyn* TK), mouse *LynB*, human *LYNB*, human *LYNA* Y32F, *LYN* variants resistant to shLyn and human *BRCA1* (C61G, L1407P, A1708E) mutants were generated using the Quickchange Lightning site-directed mutagenesis kit (Agilent Technologies, Stockport, Cheshire, UK) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Primers and templates used are listed in **Table S5**. Successful mutagenesis was verified by sequence analysis. WT or mutagenized ORFs were then inserted into a Gateway modified pWPI lentiviral vector (Regan et al., 2012) by LR reaction. WPI lentiviral vectors carrying HA-wt BRCA1, BRCA1 mutants (C61G, L1407P, A1708E) or ESRP1-FLAG ORFs were obtained following a similar strategy (further

details in **Table S5**; the ESRP1 plasmid was kindly provided by Prof Klaus Holzmann) (Leontieva and Ionov, 2009).

Viral supernatants were generated by co-transfection of the expression vector and two packaging vectors (psPAX2 and pMD2.G) into HEK293T cells. Cells were refed with fresh medium (DMEM/10% FBS; ThermoFisher) after 24 hours. Supernatants were harvested 48 and 72 hours after transfection, checked for absence of replication-competent virus and stored at -80°C until use. Lentiviruses derived from pWPI and pHIV-H2BmRFP plasmids were concentrated by ultracentrifugation (50,000g, 2 hours at 4°C). Relative lentiviral titre was determined by transducing NIH 3T3 cells using serial dilutions of the viral preparations. Freshly isolated primary cells were resuspended in viral supernatant (shRNA-carrying vectors) or concentrated viral particles in growth medium (overexpression vectors) and plated on to Matrigel or plastic as required for the specific assay. After 24 hours, medium was replaced with fresh medium (Regan et al., 2012). Puromycin (Sigma) (1.5 µg/ml) was added to culture medium of cells transduced PLKO.1 lentiviral vectors 36 hours after infection.

Generation and expression of LYN-GFP fusion proteins

ORFs for human *LYNA* and *LYNB* were cloned into pEGFP-N3 (EcoRI/BamHI). Primers and templates used are listed in **Table S5**. MDA-MB-231 cells were transiently transfected with pEGFP-N3-LYN A or pEGFP-N3-LYN B plasmids using Lipofectamine 3000 Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions. After 48 hrs cells were fixed, counterstained with DAPI and analysed by confocal microscopy.

In vitro and in vivo Dasatinib treatment

For *in vitro* experiments culture medium with a range of Dasatinib concentrations (Selleckchem, Stratech, Newmarket, Suffolk, UK) was added to cells 24 hours after plating and replaced every other day. Sigmoidal curves from dose-response data were generated using Prism software.

For *in vivo* treatment, Dasatinib monohydrate (Selleckchem) was dissolved in DMSO at 20 mg/mL and stored in aliquots at -20°C. Aliquots were thawed and diluted in 5.1% polyethylene glycol (PEG-400) and 5.1% Tween 80 (vehicle, VEH) before use. Mice were subjected to a single intraperitoneal (IP) injection of Dasatinib (DAS) (15 mg/Kg) daily. Control mice were treated with an equivalent concentration of DMSO dissolved in vehicle. Caliper measurements of tumour width (W) and length (L) were recorded every other day and tumour volumes were calculated using the formula $(L \times W^2)/2$.

In vivo conditional Lyn knock-down

Pairs of complementary DNA oligonucleotides (**Table S5**), encoding shLyn#2 (shLyn) or shScr, were annealed and cloned into a pENTRTM/H1/TO vector (ThermoFisher Scientific). The H1/TO-shLyn or -shScr cassette was then transferred into a Gateway-modified pSEW lentiviral vector (Regan et al., 2012) via LR recombination. ORF of Tetracycline repressor (TetR) was amplified from pcDNATM6/TR plasmid (ThermoFisher Scientific) (**Table S5**) and cloned into a pHIV-H2BmRFP lentiviral vector. Primary mouse *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* mammary tumour cells (line #2) were transduced using pHIV-RFP-TetR and pSEW-GFP-TO-H1(-shScr or -shLyn) lentiviral vectors. Cells positive for both GFP and RFP expression were then sorted on a FACS Aria flow cytometer (BD Biosciences) and assessed for *Lyn* knock-down *in vitro* in the absence or in the presence of doxycycline (0.5 ug/ml). 250,000 (shLyn- or shScr-) cells were orthotopically injected into the fourth right mammary fat pad of nude mice. Mice were randomized to either a control (DOX-) or a doxycycline (DOX+) diet (TD.09761, Harlan Teklad, Harlan, Indianapolis, USA).

Tumour volumes were calculated from caliper measurements of tumour width (W) and length (L) using the formula $(L \times W^2)/2$.

Immunofluorescence staining

For immunofluorescence analysis cells were grown in 8-well chamber slides (BD Biosciences) in 3D culture conditions (BD Biosciences). Cells were fixed in 4% formalin for 20 minutes and washed with PBS-glycine (0.7%) before blocking with PBS/0.1% Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA)/0.2% Triton X-100/0.05% Tween-20/10% goat serum for 1.5 hours.

Cultured MCF10A 3D acini were incubated for 2 hours with antibodies to Ki-67 (clone MM1) diluted 1:50 or to integrin- α 6 (clone GoH3) diluted 1:100 in blocking buffer prior to incubation with Alexa Fluor® 488 Goat Anti-Mouse or Donkey Anti-Rat secondary antibodies, respectively, for 1 hour. All incubation steps were carried out at room temperature. Counterstaining with DAPI was then followed by mounting using the ProLong Antifade agent (ThermoFisher Scientific).

Indirect TUNEL was performed using The ApopTag® Red In Situ Apoptosis Detection Kit (Merck Millipore) following the manufacturer's protocol. Slides were analysed on a Zeiss LSM 710 confocal microscope using a 20X objective.

Phospho-Histone H3 immunohistochemical staining

Immunohistochemistry was carried out following standard procedures. Fresh sections were cut from formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded tumour tissue. Dewaxed and re-hydrated slices underwent antigen retrieval in citrate buffer, pH 6.0 (Sigma) in a pressure cooker for 5 min before incubation with a 3% hydrogen peroxide solution for 20 min and then blocking in 1% BSA/0.1% Tween-20/TBS for 1 hour. Incubation with anti-phospho-Histone H3 (S10) antibodies

(rabbit polyclonal, #9701, Cell Signaling Technology; diluted 1:200 in blocking buffer) was performed overnight at 4°C. Detection was carried out using the EnVision+System-HRP kit for rabbit primary antibody (Dako, Ely, Cambridgeshire, UK). Sections were then counterstained with hematoxylin and mounted. Images were acquired using an Olympus BX43 microscope with a 20x/0.50 Ph1 objective.

PIN1 Immunohistochemistry and analysis of BRCA1 tumour TMA

PIN1 immunohistochemistry (IHC) was carried out by the Northern Ireland Biobank. Briefly, wax was removed from Formalin-Fixed Paraffin-Embedded (FFPE) tissue by three washes with Bond Dewax solution (Leica, Milton Keynes, UK) at 72 °C, three washes with alcohol, and three washes with Bond Wash solution (Leica). Proteins were prepared for antibody binding by incubating in Bond Epitope Retrieval 1 solution (Leica) at 100 °C for 20 min. Slides were then washed three times with Bond Wash solution. Incubation with primary antibody (anti-PIN1 Sc-46660) at 1:200 dilution was carried out for 15 min. The wash step was repeated before blocking in peroxide for 5min, washing again, and incubating in Post Primary anti-mouse antibody for 8 min. Antibody detection with DAB was carried out using the Bond Polymer Refine Detection kit (Leica) according to the manufacturer's instructions, counterstained in haematoxylin and mounted.

PIN1 scoring was based on a scale of 0-4 where 0 represented no visible staining of PIN1, 1 represents low, 2 represents medium, 3 represents high and 4 represents very high, as per the examples in **Figure 4**. Each of three cores per patient was scored independently; the highest score of the three was used as the overall score.

Isoform specific expression analysis by Affymetrix

The human LYN A isoform can be detected specifically by the microarray feature 3098998 on the Affymetrix Human Exon 1.0ST arrays. To establish LYN A's levels in human breast cancers, we extracted its isoform-specific expression across 177 previously published breast carcinomas enriched for the triple negative phenotype (Braso-Maristany et al., 2016; Gazinska et al., 2013) (ArrayExpress accession number E-MTAB-570) and across a panel of breast cancer cell lines (Heiser et al., 2012). For each breast cancer sample, immunohistochemistry-based and PAM50 derived breast cancer subtypes, as well as breast cancer cell line subtypes were retrieved from the original publications, respectively (Gazinska et al., 2013; Heiser et al., 2012).

Isoform specific expression analysis by RNAseq

Level-3 RNAseq data and overall survival was downloaded from TCGA breast cancer (TCGA, 2012). LYNA and LYNB isoforms were manually identified as uc003xsk.* and uc003xsl.* (see **Figure S13** for details). Ratios were calculated using raw RSEM values and log transformed for brevity. PAM50 classification was performed as described (Perou et al., 2000). Statistical analyses and respective data plots were generated in R version 3.2.2.

LYN pull-down for Tandem Mass Tag (TMT) labelling

MDA-MB-231 (LYN KD, LYN-A*, LYN-B*, LYN-YF*) cells were plated in T175 flasks and after two days were either serum-starved or left untreated overnight. The following day starved cells were treated with 50 ng ul⁻¹ EGF for two hours. Next, both treated and untreated cells were lysed in 1% IGEPAL CA-630, 150 mM NaCl, 1mM MgCl₂, 50 mM Tris pH 7.5, 5% glycerol, 10 mM Sodium Fluoride, 1 mM Sodium Orthovanadate, 10 mM Sodium Pyrophosphate, 100 mM β-Glycerophosphate and Complete Protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche).

After centrifugation (14000 *g* for 15 min at 4°C), cell lysates (3 mg of protein) were pre-cleared with protein A-sepharose beads (GE Healthcare) for 45 min at 4°C prior to incubation with anti-LYN antibodies (rabbit polyclonal (44), sc-15, Santa Cruz) overnight at 4°C. After incubation with protein A-sepharose beads for 45 min at 4°C, immunoprecipitates were pulled down by centrifugation (900 *g* for 5 min at 4°C), washed three times with lysis buffer, twice with lysis buffer devoid of IGEPAL CA-630 and after removal of the supernatants samples were stored at -80 °C until being processed for TMT labelling.

TMT Labelling and High pH reversed-phase chromatography

Pull-down samples were digested with trypsin while on the beads (2µg trypsin; 37°C, overnight), labelled with Tandem Mass Tag (TMT) ten plex reagents according to the manufacturer's protocol (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, LE11 5RG, UK) and the labelled samples pooled.

The pooled sample was evaporated to dryness, resuspended in 5% formic acid and then desalted using a SepPak cartridge according to the manufacturer's instructions (Waters, Milford, Massachusetts, USA). Eluate from the SepPak cartridge was again evaporated to dryness and resuspended in buffer A (20 mM ammonium hydroxide, pH 10) prior to fractionation by high pH reversed-phase chromatography using an Ultimate 3000 liquid chromatography system (Thermo Scientific). The sample was loaded onto an XBridge BEH C18 Column (130Å, 3.5 µm, 2.1 mm X 150 mm, Waters, UK) in buffer A and peptides eluted with an increasing gradient of buffer B (20 mM Ammonium Hydroxide in acetonitrile, pH 10) from 0-95% over 60 minutes. The resulting fractions were evaporated to dryness and resuspended in 1% formic acid prior to analysis by nano-LC MSMS using an Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific).

Nano-LC Mass Spectrometry

High pH RP fractions were further fractionated using an Ultimate 3000 nano-LC system in line with an Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific). Peptides in 1% (vol/vol) formic acid were injected onto an Acclaim PepMap C18 nano-trap column (Thermo Scientific). After washing with 0.5% (vol/vol) acetonitrile 0.1% (vol/vol) formic acid peptides were resolved on a 250 mm × 75 µm Acclaim PepMap C18 reverse phase analytical column (Thermo Scientific) over a 150 min organic gradient, using 7 gradient segments (1-6% solvent B over 1min., 6-15% B over 58min., 15-32%B over 58min., 32-40%B over 5min., 40-90%B over 1min., held at 90%B for 6min and then reduced to 1%B over 1min.) with a flow rate of 300 nl min⁻¹. Solvent A was 0.1% formic acid and Solvent B was aqueous 80% acetonitrile in 0.1% formic acid. Peptides were ionized by nano-electrospray ionization at 2.0kV using a stainless steel emitter with an internal diameter of 30 µm (Thermo Scientific) and a capillary temperature of 275°C.

All spectra were acquired using an Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid mass spectrometer controlled by Xcalibur 2.0 software (Thermo Scientific) and operated in data-dependent acquisition mode using an SPS-MS3 workflow. FTMS1 spectra were collected at a resolution of 120 000, with an automatic gain control (AGC) target of 200 000 and a max injection time of 50ms. Precursors were filtered with an intensity threshold of 5000, according to charge state (to include charge states 2-7) and with monoisotopic precursor selection. Previously interrogated precursors were excluded using a dynamic window (60s +/-10ppm). The MS2 precursors were isolated with a quadrupole mass filter set to a width of 1.2m/z. ITMS2 spectra were collected with an AGC target of 10 000, max injection time of 70ms and CID collision energy of 35%.

For FTMS3 analysis, the Orbitrap was operated at 50 000 resolution with an AGC target of 50 000 and a max injection time of 105ms. Precursors were fragmented by high energy collision

dissociation (HCD) at a normalised collision energy of 60% to ensure maximal TMT reporter ion yield. Synchronous Precursor Selection (SPS) was enabled to include up to 5 MS2 fragment ions in the FTMS3 scan.

TMT Data Analysis

The raw data files were processed and quantified using Proteome Discoverer software v2.1 (Thermo Scientific) and searched against the UniProt Human database (downloaded 14/09/17; 140000 sequences) plus LYNA and LYNB and LYNA_YF sequences using the SEQUEST algorithm. Peptide precursor mass tolerance was set at 10ppm, and MS/MS tolerance was set at 0.6Da. Search criteria included oxidation of methionine (+15.9949) as a variable modification and carbamidomethylation of cysteine (+57.0214) and the addition of the TMT mass tag (+229.163) to peptide N-termini and lysine as fixed modifications. Searches were performed with full tryptic digestion and a maximum of 2 missed cleavages were allowed. The reverse database search option was enabled and the data was filtered to satisfy false discovery rate (FDR) of 5%.

Quantification and Statistical Analysis

Unless otherwise stated, blots shown are representative of three independent experiments. Unless otherwise stated, all quantitation is shown as mean and SD from three independent experiments and statistical significance determined using two-tailed unpaired t-tests. Gene expression analysis by quantitative real time rtPCR is shown as mean±95% confidence intervals from three independent experiments, each of which was carried out using three technical replicates. Significance of real time rtPCR data was determined from confidence intervals (Cumming et al., 2007). *P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001.

Statistical analysis of tumour growth was conducted using the *glmer* function for generalized linear mixed models from the *lme4* package (Bates et al., 2014) in the R software (version 3.2.2). The final model accounted for the change in tumour VOLUME with time (DAY) and a DAY-by-TREATMENT interaction as fixed effects using variable random intercepts and slopes for each tumour (TUMOUR_ID). This relationship was specified as `glmer (VOLUME ~ DAY + DAY:TREATMENT + (DAY|fTUMOUR_ID), family = gaussian (link = "log)`. All modelling assumptions were confirmed to be reasonable on diagnostic residual plots.

Number of phospho-H3-positive cells in FFPE sections of grafted tumours was determined by using ImageJ image analysis software (<http://www.rsweb.nih.gov/ij/>). Automatic counting was performed on binary images (8-12 fields per tumour) after applying consecutive dilations to coalesce multiple dots within the same cell.

Band intensities on gels and western blots were also quantified using ImageJ.

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation, M.J.S., N.E.B. and G.T.; Methodology, G.T., M.dm.V.; Investigation, G.T., C.K., J.C., I.A-R. and H.K.; Writing – original draft, G.T., A.G. and M.J.S.; Writing – revision, G.T., A.G., M.dm.V. and M.J.S.; Formal analysis, H.M. and A.G.; Funding acquisition, N.E.B. and M.J.S.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Figure Legends

Figure 1 LYN is positively regulated by c-KIT in normal mammary cells. (A) Flow cytometry of primary mammary cells stained with CD45, CD24 and Sca-1 antibodies. CD45⁺ leukocytes (purple) were gated out (top plot) and the CD45⁻ cells (bottom plot) gated to define Basal (CD24^{+/low} Sca-1⁻; red), Luminal ER- (CD24^{+/high} Sca-1⁻; green), and Luminal ER+ (CD24^{+/high} Sca-1⁺; blue) epithelial cell populations. **(B)** Expression pattern of *c-Kit*, *Scf* and *Lyn* splicing transcripts in mouse mammary cell populations. Semi-quantitative RT-PCR data representative of two independent isolates (four mice for each). Amplicons of the expected size using primers spanning the alternative exon for each gene are indicated. *Gapdh* was used as a control. **(C)** qrtPCR gene expression analysis of *Scf* in mouse mammary cell populations using probes for both total *Scf* (membrane-bound and soluble) or soluble *Scf* (sSCF) only. Data from two independent isolates (four mice for each), presented as relative expression levels with leukocytes as comparator. **(D)** Schematic of LYN isoforms showing the 21 amino acid insertion (black residues) in the N-terminal domain of LYNA. **(E)** Representative western blot analysis and quantitation of c-KIT, JAK2, STAT3, AKT and ERK1/2 phosphorylation levels in protein extracts from primary mouse mammary organoids cultured on Matrigel and stimulated with SCF for the indicated times. Tubulin used as loading control. **(F)** Representative western blot analysis and quantitation of LYN autophosphorylation (Y397) and **(G)** immunoprecipitation (IP) LYN kinase assay of protein extracts from primary mouse mammary organoids cultured on Matrigel and stimulated with SCF for 0/15/30/60 minutes. **(H)** Western blot of c-Kit expression and LYN autophosphorylation (Y397) in primary mouse mammary organoids after transduction with control (shScr) or c-Kit-knockdown (shKit#1 and shKit#2) lentiviruses or **(I)** following treatment with c-KIT blocking (ACK2) or IgG isotype (IgG Ctr) antibodies. Unless otherwise stated, blots are representative of three independent experiments (mean and SD; two tailed unpaired t-tests) (in panels E and F, t-tests relative to time 0). *P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001. See also **Figure S1A**.

Figure 2. LYN promotes normal mammary cell growth. (A) Analysis of *Lyn* expression levels by qrtPCR relative to shScr cells (top) and western blot (bottom) in primary mouse mammary organoids 4 days after transduction with control (shScr) or *Lyn*-knockdown (shLyn#1 and #2) lentivirus. **(B)** Growth of mammary organoids after transduction with control (shScr) or *Lyn*-knockdown (shLyn#1 and #2) lentivirus, assessed by cell number change (left bottom panel) or organoid size (right bottom panel) relative to shScr cells, day 4 after plating. Top panels, representative images of organoids at days 6 of culture. Bar, 75 μ m. **(C)** Ki67 immunofluorescence staining (green) of control (shScr)- and shLyn-carrying mammary organoids 6 days after lentiviral transduction (DAPI nuclear counterstaining). Representative images and quantification of percentage of Ki67-positive cells. Bar, 20 μ m. **(D)** Colony-forming potential of unfractionated primary mammary epithelial cells ('All Epithelial') or Basal, Luminal ER- and Luminal ER+ subpopulations. 5000 cells from each fraction were plated on Matrigel and colony numbers determined after 12-14 days. **(E)** Growth inhibition of unfractionated primary mammary epithelial cells ('All Epithelial') or the Luminal ER- fraction transduced with control (shScr) or *Lyn*-knockdown (shLyn#1 and #2) lentivirus and seeded onto Matrigel. Cell growth assessed after 12-14 days. Representative images, left (bar, 100 μ m); quantitation, right. **(F)** Growth inhibition of MCF10A cells transduced with lentiviral vectors carrying control shRNA (shScr) or shRNA against LYN (shLyn#1 and #2). Transduced cells were grown in 3D on Matrigel and relative cell numbers assessed after 12 days of culture. Representative images of acinar structures (day 12) derived from shScr-, shLyn#1- or #2- cells are shown (scale bar, 100 μ m) together with CellTitreGlo quantitation and assessment of LYN knockdown by Western blot (GAPDH loading control). **(G)** Confocal microscope analysis of Ki67 immunofluorescence stained shScr-, shLyn#1- or #2-knockdown MCF10A cells at day 4 of culture in 3D with quantitation. DAPI was used for counterstaining. Bar, 20 μ m. Blots are representative of three independent experiments. Quantitation, mean and SD (n=3; two-tailed unpaired t-tests) except

for gene expression analysis by quantitative real time rtPCR (mean±95% confidence intervals; significance of real time rtPCR data was determined from confidence intervals; n=3 independent experiments each of 3 technical replicates per sample) (Cumming et al., 2007). *P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001. See also **Figure S1B and Figures S2, S3 and S4.**

Figure 3. LYN activity is required for growth of *Brca1*-tumor cells. **(A)** Primary cells isolated from three distinct *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* mouse mammary tumors (#1, #2 and #3) were transduced with control (shScr) or *Lyn*-knockdown lentivirus (shLyn#1 and #2), seeded at low density in adherent conditions (2D) and stained with crystal violet after 6 days. Viable cell density was determined by absorbance measurement following solubilization of the dye. Representative images of tumor cell colonies at day 6 of culture are shown. **(B)** shScr-, shLyn#1- and #2-transduced *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* tumor cells (#1, #2 and #3) seeded in Matrigel (3D) were assessed for growth after 6 days. Graphs show cell number assessed at day 5 of culture relative to shScr cells. **(C)** Ki67 immunofluorescence staining (green) of control (shScr)- and shLyn-transduced *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* tumor cells in 3D culture 6 days after lentiviral transduction. Representative images and quantification of percentage of Ki67-positive cells (n=3). Bar, 20 μ m. **(D)** Primary *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* mouse mammary tumor cells were transduced with either lentiviral shScr- and empty expression vectors (shScr), shLyn- and empty expression vectors (shLyn) or shLyn- and expression vectors carrying either an shLyn-resistant form (indicated by *) of wild-type LYNA (shLyn + LYNA*WT) or a kinase-dead LYNA mutant (shLyn + LYNA*KD). LYN protein levels determined by western blot 6 days after transduction. Graph shows cell number assessed at day 5 of culture relative to shScr cells. **(E)** HCC1937 cells were transduced with control (shScr) or *Lyn*-knockdown lentivirus (shLyn#1 and #2) and tested for LYN expression levels by western blot after 6 days. **(F)** shScr-, shLyn #1- and #2-transduced HCC1937 cells were seeded at low density in adherent conditions viable cell density was determined after 7 days as in (A). Representative images of tumor cell colonies at day 7 of culture. **(G)** *BRCA1*-mutant PDX-derived cells (BCM 3887) were transduced with control (shScr) or *LYN*-knockdown lentivirus (shLyn#1 and #2) and tested for cell viability after 10-12 days of culture in 3D on Matrigel. **(H)** Primary mouse *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* mammary tumor cells were transduced with pHIV-RFP-Tet repressor and pSEW-GFP-TO-H1 (carrying either shScr or shLyn) lentivirus. *Lyn* levels were determined in cells transduced with either inducible shScr or

shLyn and in either the presence or absence of doxycycline (DOX) by qrtPCR relative to shScr cells without DOX. **(I)** 250,000 inducible shScr or shLyn transduced cells were orthotopically injected into the fourth right mammary fat pad of nude mice. These were randomized to DOX treatment or normal diet and tumor growth monitored. Tumor volumes were calculated from caliper measurements of tumor width and length. Tumor growth curves (mean±SEM) and representative images of end-point tumors are shown. Blots are representative of three independent experiments. Unless otherwise stated, quantitation shown as mean and SD (n=3; for PDX cell experiments n=3 cell isolations from three PDX implants in 3 different mice; two-tailed unpaired t-tests), except for gene expression analysis by quantitative real time rtPCR, (mean±95% confidence intervals; significance of real time rtPCR data was determined from confidence intervals; n=3 independent experiments each of 3 technical replicates per sample) (Cumming et al., 2007). *P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001. See also **Figure S4** and **Figure S5**.

Figure 4. LYN activity is regulated by BRCA1 via the prolyl isomerase PIN1. (A) Protein extracts from TNBC cells with either wild-type *BRCA1* or impaired *BRCA1* expression were analysed for p-LYN (Y397), total LYN and GAPDH levels by Western blot. Scatter plot shows quantification of p-LYN levels normalized to total LYN levels. **(B)** Primary mouse mammary organoids were transduced with control (shScr) or *Brca1* knockdown lentivirus (shBrca1). Knockdown was assessed by qrtPCR relative to comparator shScr cells (left). shScr and shBrca1 cells were assessed for levels of phospho-c-KIT (Y719), phospho-LYN (Y397), LYN, and GAPDH by western blot after 4 days (middle). **(C)** Western blot analysis and quantitation of LYN autophosphorylation levels in primary mouse mammary organoids transduced with control (Ctr) or HA-tagged *BRCA1* (HA *BRCA1*) expression lentivirus. Blots in **(B)** and **(C)** are representative of three independent experiments. Quantitation shown as mean and SD (n=3; two-tailed unpaired t-tests) except for gene expression analysis by quantitative real time rtPCR, (mean±95% confidence intervals; significance of real time rtPCR data was determined from confidence intervals; n=3 independent experiments each of 3 technical replicates per sample) (Cumming et al., 2007). *P<0.05; **P<0.01. **Di – Dv)** Examples of PIN1 immunohistochemistry scores in breast cancer TMAs: (Di) 0, (Dii) 1, (Diii) 2, (Div) 3, (Dv) 4. DAB staining of PIN1, blue counter staining of nuclei. Bar in main panels = 500 µm; bar in inset = 50 µm. **(E)** Quantitation of PIN1 scoring in *BRCA1* mutant and sporadic TNBC TMAs (two-tailed unpaired t-test; *P<0.05). See also **Figure S6**.

Figure 5. LYN is activated in BRCA1-null cells by the prolyl isomerase PIN1. (A-C) Primary cells from *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* mouse mammary tumors **(A)**, Human HCC1937 BRCA1-deficient breast cancer cells **(B)** and BRCA1 mutant PDX-derived cells **(C)** were transduced with control (shScr) or *Pin1*-knockdown lentiviruses (shPin1#1 and #2) and lysed after 72 hrs. Protein extracts were assessed for levels of PIN1, LYN, phospho-LYN (Y397) and c-KIT (Y719) (PDX samples were not probed for phospho-KIT). Representative western blots and quantitation of phospho-LYN (Y397) levels are shown. GAPDH used as loading control. shScr-, shPin1#1- and #2-transduced *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* tumor cells and HCC1937 cells were also seeded at low density in adherent conditions and stained with crystal violet after 6 days. Cell number determined by absorbance measurement following solubilization of the dye. PDX-derived cells transduced cells were cultured for 10-12 days in 3D on Matrigel then assayed for cell viability. **(D)** Protein extracts from primary *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* mouse tumor cells transduced with vectors carrying wild-type LYNA were subjected to immunoprecipitation by anti-PIN1 or control (IgG) antibodies. Total extracts (Input) and immunoprecipitates (IP) were probed for PIN1 and LYN by western blot. **(E)** Schematic of LYN showing position of PIN1 consensus recognition sequences and proline>isoleucine mutants generated. **(F)** Representative western blot analysis of LYN phosphorylation levels at its negative regulatory phosphorylation site (Y508) in primary *BlgCre Brca1^{fl/fl} p53^{+/-}* transduced with vectors carrying wild-type LYNA or LYNA Proline-mutants (LYN P229I, LYN P197I or LYN P197I P229I). **(G)** Western blot analysis of LYN autophosphorylation and PIN1 levels in human HCC1937 cells transduced with either control (Ctr) lentivirus or virus carrying HA-tagged wild type or mutant BRCA1 (C61G, A1708E, L1407P). Blots are representative of three independent experiments. Quantitation shown as mean and SD (n=3; two tailed unpaired t-tests). *P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001. See also **Figure S7** and **Figure S8**.

Figure 6. LYNA drives migration and invasion in breast cancer cells. (A) Western blot of LYN protein levels and growth of control (shScr) and *LYNA*-knockdown MDA-MB-231 cells (shLynA) relative to shScr cells at day 0. **(B)** Migration and invasion of shScr- and shLynA-MDA-MB-231 cells, assessed by transwell assay. Representative images of end-point assays and quantification of results comparing percentages of cells per field compared to shScr cells. **(C)** Total *LYN* knockdown and *LYNA* or *LYNB* reconstitution using shLyn-resistant forms (*LYNA/B**) in MDA-MB-231 cells. Western blot showing *LYN* knockdown cells forced to express either only *LYNA* or *LYNB* and growth relative to shScr cells at day 0). **(D)** Migration and invasion of control MDA-MB-231 (shScr), *LYN*-depleted (shLyn), *LYNA* only (shLyn + *LYNA**) or *LYNB* only (shLyn + *LYNB**) expressing cells. Representative images of end-point assays and quantification of results comparing percentages of cells per field compared to shScr cells. **(E)** siCtr and siESRP1 MCF7 cells were analyzed for *LYNA::LYNB* transcript ratio and *LYN* protein levels by semi-quantitative RT-PCR (top, with quantitation) or western blot (bottom), respectively. **(F)** MDA-MB-231 cells were transduced with control (Ctr) or FLAG-tagged ESRP1 (FLAG-ESRP1) lentivirus. ESRP1 overexpression was assessed by qrtPCR (fold expression over comparator Ctr cells; upper left panel). Ctr and FLAG-ESRP1 cells were analyzed for *LYNA:LYNB* transcript ratio by semi-quantitative RT-PCR (bottom panels) and *LYN* and ESRP1 protein levels by western blot (upper right panel). Blots are representative of three independent experiments. Quantitation shown as mean and SD (n=3; two-tailed unpaired t-tests), except for gene expression analysis by quantitative real time rtPCR (mean±95% confidence intervals; significance of real time rtPCR data was determined from confidence intervals; n=3 independent experiments each of 3 technical replicates per sample) (Cumming et al., 2007). *P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001. See also **Figure S9** and **S10**.

Figure 7. The LYNA::LYNB isoform ratio is prognostic in breast cancer. (A) Representative semi-quantitative rtPCR expression analysis of *ESR1* and *LYN* levels in breast cells from reduction mammoplasty tissue separated into stromal cells, basal cells, luminal progenitors and mature luminal populations as described (Iriando et al., 2015; Lim et al., 2009; Simoes et al., 2011). Plot is representative of outcomes of four independent sorts. **(B)** Quantitation of *ESR1* expression levels confirming *ESR1* is most highly expressed in the mature luminal population (mean+SD relative to mature luminal cells; n=3 independent cell preparations; unpaired two-tailed t-test; **P<0.01). **(C)** Quantitation of relative *LYNA::B* ratio (n=4 independent cell preparations; paired two-tailed t-test; *P<0.05) in breast cell populations. **(D)** Expression of *LYNA* and *LYNB* isoforms in TCGA breast cancer data split by IHC-defined TNBC (n=112) and non-TNBC (n=470) tumors. Tumors are also color-coded based on their PAM50 molecular subtype. **(E)** For each sample shown in (D), *LYNA::B* ratio was established based on log₂ expression of *LYNA* over *LYNB*. The distribution of *LYNA::B* ratios among samples derived from normal breast tissue (data also from TCGA), TNBC and Non-TNBC were comparable when tested Wilcoxon Rank-Sum test. **(F)** Density distributions of *LYNA::B* log₂ RSEM expression ratios in TCGA breast cancer data set. 7.3 *LYNA::B* ratio cut-off indicated. **(G)** Breast cancer specific survival of patients based on *LYNA::B* isoform expression ratio from TCGA data in patient groups dichotomised at the 7.3 ratio boundary. IHC phenotype of each tumor (where known) is indicated by the colour of each data point. A high *LYNA::B* ratio selects patients with a shorter survival independent of the breast cancer subtype (Wilcoxon Rank-Sum test). See also **Figure S11 and S12.**